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The strategy of personnel development of organizations in the context of the national security of Ukraine

The article presents the development of theoretical and methodological foundations and practical recommendations for building a system of motivation for the development of personnel of a modern organization as an element of improving its economic security and the level of internal state security as a whole.

Keywords: *state security, economic security, personnel, personnel development, motivation of personnel development, personnel development strategy, state regulation of employment of the population.*

In recent years, the labor market of Ukraine is in a state of transformation, accompanied by certain negative consequences, in particular, associated with a decrease in labor productivity, worsening employment conditions, the spread of precarious work segment, and the like. Significant manifestations of the professional - qualification imbalance of supply and demand on the national labor market, an increase in the burden on regional labor markets, an increase in unemployment and social tension in the country, which is an element of deterioration and national security in general.

Increasing the level of both internal state security in general under these conditions, and the level of economic security of individual organizations, not least depends on building a motivation system for staff development, based on the formation and maintenance of partnerships between the state, employers and employees with an orientation towards the formation of a favorable motivational field of personnel development, which provides not only the process of creating sustainable competitive advantages of the organization, but also on intellectual potential of employees, their personal competitiveness, targeted reproduction and formation of new competencies of employees, ensuring their personal professional success in the future and demand in the labor market at different stages of their life cycle in a volatile external environment; substantiation of the personnel development strategy in the organization on the basis of productive activities with an orientation to human development priorities set at the macro level, the support of which is guaranteed by the subsystem of state economic incentives for vocational training and staff development, and taking into account the level of professional development quality of the organization's personnel.

Among the instruments for regulating the labor market, the most promising are those aimed at ensuring a balance in the market of educational services and the labor market in the conditions of transformation of the employment structure; raising the professional qualification level of personnel in accordance with the requirements of the labor market and scientific and technological progress; strengthening motivation for

work, employment and entrepreneurship based on the development of human resources.

It is advisable to conclude that employment is a complex economic category that defines socio-economic relations, and varies in forms, types and indicators. Ensuring employment of the population is the strategic goal of building a socially oriented labor market in modern conditions of development of the Ukrainian economy, the specific aspects of which are: intensifying innovation and investment activities, improving vocational and qualification training, increasing the effectiveness of active employment policy measures, improving the system of social and labor relations.

However, under the conditions of structural transformations in the Ukrainian economy, the possibilities of enhancing the effectiveness of processes occurring in the labor market are significantly limited. That is why it is necessary to create conditions for creating a competitive environment in the labor market by stimulating demand for labor, pursuing a sound policy to create new effective jobs, attracting investments in the development of promising sectors of the economy, optimizing the professional qualifications structure of the economically active population, improving the quality of human capital, promoting the development of self-employment and entrepreneurship, ensuring effective social protection of the population.

In order to ensure employment of the country's population, it is necessary:

1) at the state level, ensure: increasing labor market flexibility, redistributing the costs of passive and active measures of social protection of the population in the labor market, with the latter being preferred, helping to reduce unregulated employment, legislatively restricting the length of forced leave at the initiative of the administration, and increasing real wages, intensification of the activities of institutions that promote the employment of the population, training and retraining of personnel;

2) at the organization level to implement: coordination of the release of workers with regional and state employment programs; reduction in the number, if possible, of only low-skilled workers and those who work in the field of heavy manual labor or

outdated equipment, while retaining highly qualified personnel of the enterprise; conducting professional retraining or advanced training of employees without terminating employment contracts with them; orientation of employees to improve education and skills; creation of conditions for employees that would contribute to the growth of labor productivity (improving forms and methods of organizing production, improving the technical support of the labor process, the effective use of labor motivation);

3) on an individual level: creating an effective system of motivating each individual employee to labor mobility, increasing labor productivity, increasing his competitiveness in the labor market and the constant development of professional skills; maintaining the state of one's health and working capacity at the proper level; improvement of personal business and moral qualities.

An analysis of the above directions of ensuring employment in modern conditions indicates that one of the leading tools for ensuring it at both the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels is the development of workers.

Thus, the theoretical justification of necessity and the development of a method for the practical implementation of the development strategy of the organization's personnel in the aspect of state regulation of employment are becoming particularly relevant.

In the Law of Ukraine "On Employment," the concept of employment is defined as "the activities of individuals related to the satisfaction of their personal and social needs in order to receive income (wages) in money or another form, as well as the activities of members of the same family, are not prohibited by law, engaged in business activities or work with business entities based on their property, including free of charge" [1].

Employment, according to the definition of L. I. Rofe, is interpreted as the activity of the population, should bring them income and requires compliance with the legislation established in the country [2]. The approach to the definition of employment

V. S. Vasilchenko [3], similar to the interpretation of L. I. Rofe, but this definition focuses on detailing the forms of individual profits from employment.

Modern aspects of personnel development management in the context of solving the strategic tasks of the enterprise are reflected in the scientific works of T. Boydela, N. Dixon, D. Megginson and M. Pedler, J. Ravenna, P. Senju, A. Tompson and J. Strickland, N. S. Gavkalova, A. A. Grishnova, A. Ya. Kibanova, A. M. Kolot, V. A. Savchenko, L. N. Shimanovskaya - Dianich, S.V. Shekshnia. Applying the attributive approach proposed by Yu. M. Komar, E. A. Lyubimova formed the attributive structure of the organization's personnel development management system, including 3 subsystems: human, professional and sustainable development, in accordance with which the author developed a conceptual model for enterprise personnel development [4]. L. N. Cherchik proposes the development and implementation of personnel development strategies in accordance with a three-level hierarchical pyramid - thanks to a clear hierarchical structure, a strategic set is being phased in, which allows achieving strategic goals at each hierarchical level and applying a process approach to substantiating a personnel development strategy, includes a number of interrelated stages in the strategic management system [5].

Proclaimed as part of the Europe 2020 Strategy, the flagship initiative “Program for New Skills and Jobs”, which aims to develop the labor resources of the EU member states, provides for the empowerment of people through the development of their skills throughout life and adaptation to new circumstances and professional changes in the conditions of an economy based on knowledge and innovations, based on continuing professional education and training, which includes in-house training and staff development [6]. Considering Ukraine's chosen direction towards European integration, domestic enterprises are faced with the urgent problem of creating a modern personnel development management system based on the concept of lifelong learning, the innovative essence of which “is the coalescence in its framework of two logics - the logic of education (development of citizens' abilities) and the logic of

industry (optimal use of human resources)”, which allows employees to satisfy their own educational needs, using the services as a specialist leased educational institutions, and without a middle one at the enterprise at the place of employment through high-quality training based on productive activities. This, in turn, necessitates the development of theoretical, methodological and scientific foundations for managing the development of enterprise personnel, taking into account new approaches to European human resource management.

Considering the substantial component of the personnel development process, the authors focus on such elements as: vocational training, professional adaptation, assessment of candidates for a vacant position, the current periodic assessment of personnel, assessment and planning of a staff’s career and career promotion, work with personnel reserve, improving the social structure of personnel [7], including not only the sphere of personnel development, but also the components of the process of its formation. Other authors, figuring out the essence of personnel development, do not focus on its basic elements, but focus on the results of this process, given its strategic nature and focus not only on the professional development of the employee, but also the improvement of his personal qualities [8].

Meanwhile, it should be noted that most authors do not indicate a direct relationship between qualitative shifts in the field of personnel development and building up the labor potential of a business entity, nor do they pay due attention to the problem of the dependence of the growth of the individual competitiveness of the employee and the extension of the period of his labor activity on this basis from the results of his personal harmonious development directly at the enterprise at the place of employment. Coverage of these strategic issues, as well as the formation of the development strategy of the organization’s personnel in the aspect of state regulation of employment in general, in our opinion, has not yet received sufficient coverage in the studies.

Based on the foregoing, the purpose of the article is to develop a general mechanism for working with groups of personnel reserve within the framework of the development system of managerial personnel in hierarchical organizational systems with a direct account of the characteristics of such systems.

In modern conditions, the determining factor for ensuring a steady economic recovery of the state is the stable functioning and dynamic development of first of all the organizations of the country's industrial complex, which initiate scientific and technological transformations through the generation, integration and operation of knowledge as an asset, and ensure the receipt of economic benefits in the current period and strategic perspective [9]. The key to competitiveness and long-term success of business entities is precisely their employees who have received a certain level of competence, the ability to use the acquired knowledge in practice, to improve their own activities on their basis, which leads to a constant tightening of the requirements of employers for the quality of the workforce. However, in the context of the aggravation of the financial and economic crisis in the country, there has been a significant slowdown in the rate of staff development, which is due to a reduction in employers' investments in professional training and advanced training of employees, insufficient interest of workers in their own development of the enterprise at the place of employment through high-quality training based on productive activities due to the inability to occupy jobs with high professional requirements, career growth, a substantial increase in the levels of differentiation of wages depending on the degree of training.

Highly appreciating the contribution of scientists and economists, it should be noted that in the framework of ongoing research on the formation of an effective system of motivation for the development of personnel of industrial enterprises, priority attention was paid to the issues of building a set of means of motivational influence, encouraging employees to learn and professional development, and partially raised the problem of the coordination of interests and expectations economic entities interact in

the framework of the transformation process “data - information - knowledge - skills - skills - experience - competencies - competence” and the application of adequate ways to stimulate them to cooperate, not only with the aim of ensuring the survival and sustainable development of industrial enterprises, but also building the potential of workers' competitiveness, optimizing the use of skilled labor and solving on this basis the problem of economically active employment the country's population.

In modern conditions, the development of human resources through internal company training and the development of production personnel is considered not only as a condition for increasing the competitiveness of industrial enterprises, but also as a way to solve the problem of employment of the country's population, requires the development at the state level of a policy for training and developing the professional skills of workers during life in the framework of ongoing activities in order to increase their productivity and labor profusion. The practice of state regulation of the sphere of vocational training and development of workers in the advanced countries of the world community indicates the expansion of the field of application of economic stimulants that affect the dynamics of reproduction and accumulation of the country's labor potential, quality components of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel. The expediency of their use is, in particular, in the conditions of a severe budget deficit in Ukraine, due to the fact that they provide a redistribution of funding sources for the professional development of personnel at enterprises between the government, entrepreneurs and employees while maintaining the parity of interests of all interested parties.

For economic entities, priority is given to economic incentives, which do not limit their actions in determining their own goals and choosing the means for their implementation, strengthen the incentives to perform a specific type of activity in the hope of obtaining economic benefits for the results achieved. This provides the possibility of additional assignment of a certain share of benefits and the satisfaction of existing needs at a higher level. Guaranteed by economic incentives, the benefits are

encouraging, while imposing economic responsibility for the quality of the activity and the level of its effectiveness. All this provides the basis for the widespread use of economic incentives in the formation of the mechanism of state regulation of the sphere of vocational training and development of workers.

In the context of globalization, there is a need to move from a personnel development process isolated in the framework of a separate enterprise to coordination and cooperation of efforts in this area of state bodies, educational institutions, entrepreneurial structures, employees, and public organizations. However, it should be borne in mind that each of the participants in this process has its own narrow economic interests, and the continuity of vocational education and training depends on how much they are agreed between all interested parties.

The subsystem of economic incentives for vocational training and employee development at the state level should, first of all, take into account and coordinate the interests of various groups of economic agents in this field. The process of internal company training and development of production personnel will be continuous and dynamic if, *ceteris paribus*, each of its participants, developing and strengthening their own activities, can take advantage of the external benefits guaranteed by the state, while the results achieved by it are the basis for further progressive the development of this process and the satisfaction of both the private interests of its partners and public needs. This is only possible in a situation where a motivational field will be created by the system of state incentives for vocational training and development of workers, encouraging business entities to proactively coordinate their competing interests.

The potential opportunity to form and ensure the positive dynamics of partnerships between employees, employers, and the state is due to the identical orientation of the motives that push economic entities to be involved in the development of human resources and create on this basis a basis for strengthening their own competitiveness, stabilizing their position and building up financial opportunities

Thus, the state economic incentive for vocational training and development of workers is a structured complex of unstable competitive advantages guaranteed by the state, provides economic subjects with a temporary priority right to realize their own economic interests and encourages them to proactively coordinate these competing interests in order to ensure continuing professional education and training, which includes in-house training and development production staff.

The opportunity to take advantage of special tax benefits, the right to exempt from paying taxes or loans, paid for training, is classified as a duplicate, unsustainable competitive advantage guaranteed by the state to economic entities, accumulating their own resources in order to further invest in staff development. The prospects for obtaining these unsustainable competitive advantages over a certain period of time, subject to the conditions proposed by the state, will contribute to the formation of positive expectations among economic entities regarding the possibility of further gaining and maintaining competitive advantages of a high rank, that is, a number of internal benefits: the ability of employees to constantly improve themselves and develop, building up their innovative potential and personal competitiveness and profession mobility, optimization and exchange rate stability of the personnel of the enterprise, increasing the parameters of productivity and efficiency of its activities, etc. This, in turn, will help to eliminate the imbalance between demand and supply of highly qualified labor force in the labor market, the formation of the foundation for solving the problem of optimizing employment economically active population of the country, reducing government spending on social insurance against unemployment, ensuring social security prosperity in society.

At the same time, an important factor that will contribute to the formation of an effective system of state economic incentives for vocational training and development of workers is the real provision in practice to economic entities of all the unstable competitive advantages that were previously declared by the state. Otherwise, the receipt of negative experience by economic entities due to violation by the state of their

obligations will further lead to the formation of negative expectations regarding the feasibility of carrying out activities in the field of continuous training and staff development and only hinder its progress.

The experience of economically developed countries indicates that the stimulation of the processes of professional training and staff development involves the provision by the state of a specific set of financial and credit benefits, which include:

- withdrawal from the object of taxation of its individual components;
- exemption from taxation of certain categories of payers;
- reduction of tax rates for certain categories of payers;
- approval of the tax-free minimum of the tax object;
- deduction from a certain amount of tax;
- deferral of tax collection;
- application of special lending regimes.

In the context of strengthening integration processes for Ukraine, it is extremely important to study and draw on the positive experience of other countries in the field of state stimulation of the processes of vocational training and development of the labor force and its adaptation to the realities of the domestic economy, which today operates in a state of severe budget deficit, an increase in the overall unemployment rate and a decrease the employment threshold of the economically active middle-aged population, low level of satisfaction of demand for highly qualified labor force.

Under such conditions, it is advisable, from our point of view, to formulate the possibility of practical application of the following financial and credit benefits when forming a system of state economic incentives for vocational training and the development of the workforce, as an instrument for regulating employment of the population:

- exemption from payment of contributions to the social insurance of the employer, organizes retraining courses for the unemployed at his enterprise;

- provide for enterprises that carry out on an ongoing basis the financing of professional training of personnel in production a tax reduction if the production has a profit;

- the provision of tax benefits to employers who conclude agreements between enterprises on the joint use of labor and jointly bear the costs of its vocational training;

- the provision of tax incentives to labor rental companies that provide employees with professional training and retraining, permanent work and provide them with a package of social services subject to their temporary employment in various enterprises in the profile of this company;

- taxation at preferential rates of enterprises, allocate funds to specialized training funds to ensure continuing professional education;

- tax incentives for enterprises providing jobs for the practical training of university students

- tax credits for the employer, who provided the first job for a graduate of a higher school

- tax discounts for the enterprise participating in the update program

In forming the enterprise development strategy, the leading role should be assigned to personnel development, it is a key factor in productivity and effectiveness, and also determines the efficiency of using the rest of the enterprise's resources. High-quality and timely professional development of personnel allows you to get socio-economic returns to the employee himself, the enterprise and the country as a whole, and, as a result, the state security of Ukraine.

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